

Social Transformation for Water Stewardship
through Scaling Up Citizen Science

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	6
1. OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT	7
2. THE OTTERS DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	8
2.1 Aims and objectives of the OTTERS DMP	8
2.2 Overall structure of the OTTERS DMP	9
2.3 DMP updates during the lifetime of the project	11
2.4 Long-term data management	11
3. DATA COLLECTION	12
3.1 Data information	12
3.2 Organization of data collected	13
3.3 Data collected for each OTTERS Work Package	14
Work Package 1	14
Work Package 2	15
Work Package 3	17
Work Package 4	18
Work Package 5	20
Work Package 6	21
4. DATA DOCUMENTATION	24
5. DATA STORAGE AND BACKUP	24
6. DATA ACCESS	27
7. DATA SHARING AND REUSE	28
Data security:	28
Data Interoperability:	28
8. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE	29
References	32

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the preliminary version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the OTTERS project and provides an initial summary of the main elements to take into account in the definition of the OTTERS data management policy to be used by project partners throughout the project activities. The DMP will provide indications about the management of all the data generated during the implementation of project activities, including how data will be collected, managed, stored, and made available during the project and how they will be shared upon its completion.

The DMP is a living document that will be updated during the project lifetime according to the project's progress and emerging needs. The final revision of the OTTERS DMP will be provided at the end of the project (M30) and will also provide more details about the long-term management and preservation of project data.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CS	Citizen Science
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DAP	Distributed Data Access Protocols
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OIM	Ocean Information Model and Vocabulary
R&I	Research and Innovation
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT

The OTTERS – Social Transformation for Water Stewardship through Scaling Up Citizen Science – is a Horizon Europe project funded by the Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Actions programme called HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-05.

The OTTERS Project aims to promote societal transformation for marine and freshwater stewardship through scaling up citizen science.

OTTERS will support the coordination of EU citizen science initiatives focused on marine and freshwater, aiming to:

- Accelerate the creation and adoption of technical, legal, and ethical standards for citizen science protocols and methods.
- Examine the effectiveness of citizen science in societal transformation towards sustainable aquatic ecosystem stewardship.
- Pilot cross-community, watershed-based Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns.

The OTTERS vision is to demonstrate effective embedding of citizen science in initiatives seeking societal transformation for sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems. OTTERS wishes to not only generate data but through citizen science also contribute to changing hearts, increasing care for marine and freshwater ecosystems and fostering a sense of agency, leading to the contribution of healthy ecosystems to human wellbeing.

2. THE OTTERS DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

2.1 Aims and objectives of the OTTERS DMP

Horizon Europe projects stipulate that beneficiaries make their data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The aim of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to promote the adoption of good data management practices by the OTTERS project consortium, enabling the accessibility of the data generated during the project lifetime and beyond, and ensuring long-term data preservation as the ultimate goals of a successful data management. The DMP is therefore an essential aspect of each HE project, and it must be thoroughly planned from the early stages of the implementation phase.

This deliverable aims at describing the overall data management process within OTTERS: how data will be collected, managed, stored and made available during the project, and how they will be shared upon its completion. It is worth pointing out that a proper data management plan can mitigate the risk of data loss or other threats that could render the data illegible or unusable (e.g. the obsolescence of software). The DMP is designed to be a living and working document, to be updated regularly upon need. The project coordinator will be tasked with overseeing and updating the DMP in collaboration with project partners, as well as for issues related to DMP compliance and data management in general. The project coordinator is also responsible for the provision of documents to be filled out by partners to support DMP updates.

Effective data management is not an end in itself, but rather serves as the essential pathway that enables the exploration of knowledge and the development of new ideas. It also facilitates the integration and reuse of data and knowledge by the community following the process of publishing data. For this reason, all data collected and generated during the OTTERS project will be managed following the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

2.2 Overall structure of the OTTERS DMP

OTTERS will consider the guidelines of the HE Open Access policy and recommendations of the Open Research Data pilot, as well as following the FAIR data and Open Science principles. Standards regarding data management, sharing, security, and privacy will be assessed in WP1 and will be agreed upon with consortium members, helping outline how data will be processed or generated within the project and beyond; what methodology and standards will be adopted; whether, which and how data will be shared and/or made open; how data will be curated and preserved during and after the project; and how data between the EU and Neighbouring Countries can be transferred.

The OTTERS Data Management Plan will determine the data that will be re-used/produced within the project, the repositories to be used for data storage and organisation, and the methods to make them publicly available, for the benefit of science and society. The DMP will entail the following types of data: (1) Technical reports and project deliverables: The quality assurance plan will detail the management procedures required to guarantee that project documents are correctly and efficiently produced, updated, distributed and stored. We will aim to make as many project deliverables as possible public; (2) Research data generated during assessment through literature review and consultations with other past and ongoing citizen science initiatives, workshops organised throughout the project, and analyses on the impacts of CS initiatives in the water domain, as well as lessons learnt from the three pilot campaigns planned.

The project will seek a balance between openness and protection of information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) if any, privacy concerns, security etc. In case project partners need to keep specific parts of their research data closed, the choice will be explicitly justified in the DMP.

The key results will be disseminated among all involved stakeholders and will contribute to the EU R&I agenda on CS via reports, whitepapers and policy briefs. Research data will be retained only where the risks to the research subjects are low, as determined by a Privacy Impact Assessment. Depending on the identified risks, the data may be anonymized or pseudonymized prior to archiving, and the conditions determined for access to the data by other researchers. Some restrictions may also be needed to protect commercially sensitive data.

For peer-reviewed publications, the authors will opt for “green access” as a default whenever possible while guaranteeing that results will be immediately available (based on publishers’ policies). When timely open-access dissemination is not possible by following the “green access” model, the authors will opt for the “gold open access” model. Open access publications will be available centrally via OpenAIRE. When needed, as in the case of delays in peer-reviewed publications out of the authors’ control, pre-prints of the manuscripts will be made available on repositories such as arXiv (arxiv.org) or bioRxiv (biorxiv.org); and citizen-generated measurements and data throughout the project will be made available via the use of a layer of Ocean Interoperability Data Space, which will provide accessibility to support for the heterogeneous and increasingly growing set of data and services available for the Oceans and will directly contribute to a European Ocean Data Space and, where feasible, to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) . The Ocean Interoperability Data Space will be supported by the semantic Ocean Information Model and Vocabulary (OIM) and further by services for semantically enhanced data discovery and datasets.

Through the integration and the accessibility of the data via various complementary platforms (ILIAD, EMODnet, Marinomica, BioFresh, WISE-Freshwater, etc.) the generated output will be supported by the open Ocean Data Platform of C4IR Ocean – with the associated Contextualisation services powered by Cognite Data Fusion for time and space interoperability resolution mappings and harmonisation and will be enhanced by new Digital Earth and Digital Twin of the Oceans services with the aim of reaching the goals of the EU Digital Strategy.

This deliverable describes the Data Collection within OTTERS in Section 3, which presents the methods of data collection for each work package, as indicated by the work package leaders. For each work package, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable: type of data, aim of the data, and formats. The Data Collection section is essential to give a brief description of the data, including any existing data or third-party sources that will be used, providing information about its content, type and coverage.

The Data Documentation section (see Section 4) details how data will be documented to ensure that new members of the OTTERS team and/or any possible (secondary) users are able to understand and reuse the data. Additional information will be provided about the metadata used to provide indications about the identification and access to the data.

The Data Storage and Backup section (Section 5) describes where and how the data generated by the project activities will be stored. Information about the IT infrastructure used will also be provided. This section also explains the general rules adopted by the project in order to preserve the main part of data generated.

The Data Access section (see Section 6) mainly describes the level of data confidentiality and the responsibility of the individual organisations, within OTTERS, involved in the data collection process, while the Data Sharing and reuse section (see Section 7) will detail how the data will be shared and where it will be deposited.

Finally, Section 8 will detail the procedures to ensure the privacy of Participants to OTTERS activities.

2.3 DMP updates during the lifetime of the project

The DMP will be updated regularly upon need. The Project Coordinator will be responsible for the data management with the active support of Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders. The content of the data management plan will be reanalyzed and enriched in each update of the deliverable according to the project implementation progress and new types of data collected.

2.4 Long-term data management

To be useful, findable and reusable over the long-term, public data will be stored on Zenodo and will be automatically assigned a persistent identifier, namely a DOI, to allow for easy citation and discoverability. This practice will also mitigate the risk of data loss. More information about the long-term management of data internal to OTTERS consortium will be provided in the next updates of the Data Management Plan. Datasets used in journal publications will also be made available, unless they contain sensitive and private information, in accordance to journal requirements.

3. DATA COLLECTION

3.1 Data information

During the OTTERS project, various types of data will be collected. This section describes the methods of data collection for each work package as indicated by the work package leaders. For each work package, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable.

Types of Data:

In research projects, the following type of data may be collected and documented:

- **Observational:** data captured through observation of an activity and/or a behaviour in real-time (and, therefore, usually irreplaceable). The collection usually may require human observation, surveys and instruments to record the information.
- **Experimental:** data obtained in controlled situations through the active intervention of researchers, who design an activity (called experiment) to collect data. They can be reproduced if needed, but it may be expensive.
- **Simulation:** data generated reproducing a real-world system, usually used to determine what would happen in certain conditions.
- **Derived or Compiled:** data derived upon transformation of existing data sets to create new data. They can be reproduced if lost, but it is very time-consuming and it could be expensive.
- **Reference or Canonical:** it refers to data used to categorise and/or classify other data. They could be static or changing over time.
- **Event-related:** data collected during events. As they are real-time events, they are irreplaceable. They can include personal data of participants, and GDPR will be applied.

It is worth pointing out that these categories can overlap, and data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself (e.g. event-related data could also be considered observational data upon certain conditions).

Aim of the data and the process of data collection

For each Work Package a short description of the aim of the data produced linked to the objectives of the Work Package is provided, together with a short description of the process of the data collection that will be applied.

Format of the data and estimated size

Research data come in various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, discipline and instrument specific, etc. For each WP, it will describe the format of the data produced, with the ultimate goal to facilitate the accessibility and interoperability of the data, giving preferences to open and standard formats. This information will be updated in the next versions of OTTERS DMP according to project developments.

3.2 Organization of data collected

The data collected within OTTERS will be organised taking into consideration the following aspects, as far as applicable.

Version Control

To overcome the challenge of managing and tracking research materials during the course of research, especially in collaborative projects, data will be organised to keep track of different versions of the datasets, through the application of a version control system. A version control system (or revision control system) is a system that tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files and, in some cases, directories over time.

Improving the ability to consistently track and retrieve each version of a file can lead to more efficient collaboration and increased accuracy of research results. Through the version control system, the risk of losing information after modifications is minimised. Versioning is important for long term-research data management where metadata and/or files are updated over time. For scientific projects wherein different parties are involved, it is advised to use a data storage system with version control function to prevent losing of data.

File naming convention

With the overall aim to make the data accessible (and ultimately foster reproducible research), OTTERS datasets will be carefully named by choosing file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines. Names should be meaningful so as to make it easier for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used.

3.3 Data collected for each OTTERS Work Package

Each work package is responsible for the data management of their own tasks. Overall responsibility of data management falls to the project coordinator and leader of WP6 (project management): The American University Armenia (AUA).

Work Package 1

The WP leader (ECSA) will oversee the collection of data through the use of templates and data collection forms (including event-based ones). The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data: Potential catalogues or compilations of CS-related standards and best practices.

Source of Pre-Existing data: Free databases of citizen science projects (such as the EU Citizen Science platform), or open source databases or platforms such as the EOSC (<https://eosc-portal.eu/>).

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: Each material that will be collected will be checked for permission to use and will be credited.

Generated data will come from voluntary stakeholders participating in the project.

Type of data collected:

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

The overall objective of WP1 is to enable and accelerate the co-creation of standards for citizen science protocols and methods, particularly in marine and freshwater domains to be tied to European Marine Observation and Data Network and to the Digital Twins of the Oceans (EDITO, Iliad, etc.). This will include reports and factsheets to standardise protocols and methods for water-related citizen science and compliance with WFD and MSFD monitoring requirements as well as discussing standardisation within FAIR and legal contexts.

Process of data collection:

WP1 will collect or generate data from questionnaires, consent forms, interviews, workshops, discussions, and learning sessions involving stakeholders and citizens that participate in the project, both online and in person.

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .XLM
- ✓ .DOC / .DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

The size of the data will vary depending on the number of stakeholders/participants, and the number of projects reviewed in the mapping stage. Guidelines for the standardisation of data structures

We will re-use freely available data, published in the form of scientific articles, openly available on databases or platforms, and information on current and previous citizen science projects around water for task 1.1 (identification and benchmarking of citizen science standardisation efforts)

The only other data that will be re-used is if partners have stakeholder contact details that have opted-in to be contacted in future. We may then contact the stakeholders to participate in workshops and events.

Personal data of stakeholders will not be public. Research data adapted to create outputs of the project (such as a database of citizen science projects, reports and factsheets based on workshops) will be freely available to be used as standards for future citizen science projects, by all stakeholders relevant to OTTERS, or policy and decision makers (in summary form).

Work Package 2

The WP leader (CSGI) will oversee the collection of data through the use of desk research, surveys and conducted workshops. The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data:

Source of Pre-Existing data: Data collected in WP1, CS-related catalogues, reports, legislations, other projects, interviews, and workshops.

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: OTTERS Grant Agreement, WP1 output, ethical considerations (described in section 8).

Type of data collected

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

WP2 is primarily aimed at contributing to the discussions on scaling up and improving the use of citizen science in marine and freshwater domains by conducting reviews, assessments, and discussions of the effectiveness of citizen science for research and innovation, and on citizens' awareness, ocean literacy, and behaviour with respect to marine and freshwater environments. This will explore the experience and practices of specialised stakeholders, such as fishing communities, sailors, recreational divers, ferry and ship crew, hobbyists, school students, members or volunteers of local associations (cultural, environmental and recreational), etc. All assessments and discussions will include reflections from a gender and inclusivity perspective.

Process of data collection:

In order to elaborate the necessary data collection, survey of the results and insights of EU projects and programs and relevant literature on effectiveness of citizen science, white papers on the effectiveness of CS, and workshops gathered the necessary data for collection.

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Work Package 3

The WP leader (21C Consultancy) will oversee the collection of data through the use of desk research, interviews, co-creation events and clustering of existing CS initiatives under the relevant campaign. The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data: Existing CS initiatives

Source of Pre-Existing data: Multiple sources and CS catalogues

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: N/A

Type of data collected:

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

WP3 aims to co-design campaigns to scale up citizen science and foster a sense of agency in water stewardship. The co-designed campaigns will offer narratives to change hearts and minds by integrating citizen science components that engage citizens, empower younger and older generations to take action, promote the practice of social innovation, ocean and water citizen and local stewardship, and achieve the social transformational goals. The campaigns will include use of citizen science tools that collect data in compliance with WFD and MSFD monitoring requirements. The campaigns will also explore possibilities of linking citizen science data into existing EU initiatives and data infrastructure consistent with recommended protocols and methods. Based on the results of WP1, WP2, and T3.1 – T3.3, the WP will develop a guidebook and toolkit for developing and implementing similar campaigns in a wide variety of regions.

Process of data collection:

The data collected will be related to the creation of a Resource Hub for CS in marine and freshwater domains, and development of guidebooks and toolbox for marine and freshwater Spring-to-sea Stewardship citizen science campaigns.

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS /.XLSX

- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Work Package 4

The information will be collected by the WP leader (NUCLIO) through different physical and online activities (workshops, hackathons, training). The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data: N/A

Source of Pre-Existing data: N/A

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: N/A

Type of data collected:

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

The WP will address the educational sector (primary to tertiary) and expert/practitioner capacity building needs. The ultimate goal of the capacity building is to have the necessary teachers, institutional capacity, and expertise for empowering citizens through education and larger collaborations to take actions to improve the monitoring of the health of the ocean and waters and to act against pollution and promote ocean stewardship. The focus of the capacity building would be to provide tools and methods to teachers and experts for encouraging young citizens to understand their role in managing the marine environment, motivated by becoming part of the decision-making process involving policy makers and other stakeholders. This will be achieved via the involvement of schools as hubs of their communities, educators as drivers and facilitators of change and students as co-creators and change makers for their communities. It will also provide other local actors, such as water advocacy groups, community development organisations or local governments, with improved skills and better access to support resources to organise campaigns that aim to use citizen science effectively.

Process of data collection:

Several types of data will be collected during project activities related to WP4. First of all, data will be collected as a result of the engagement activities with schools in order to develop Road Map for CS integration into curricula. This will be the basis to increase ocean literacy, and launch the selection of OTTERS pilot schools, the school hubs, and establish the model for the pilot interactions.

Secondly, hackathons and summer schools with teachers will be organised for a face to face training event where the guidelines (based on work done in WP2), tutorials (Tasks 3.3 and 3.4) and the science behind each of the CS programs will be presented. The event will be open to educators participating in other CS initiatives, holders of mobility grants or any other educator willing to take part in the initiative. The data collected will be about the training course on citizen science. This will include:

- Title of training course
- Institution/organisation offering the course
- Length of training course, and dates offered
- Target audience for the course
- URL to access the training course / information about the training course
- Financing of training course, including course fee, if any
- Details of what is covered in the course
- Structure of training course
- Learning goals of training course
- Evaluation of training course

The data will be mainly text and stored in a spreadsheet for better overview. An analysis of the data will be performed and shared in an appropriate format. Additionally, during the training course implementation other data will be collected and generated, such as:

- List of participants
- Slides of the presentations
- Video Recording of the interactions (recording of ZOOM or video-recording of site visit presentations)

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS /.XLSX
- ✓ .PPT /.PPTX
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format

✓ Video Format

Work Package 5

The information will be generated and collected by the WP leader (AGORA) through the use of available communication and dissemination tools and metrics. The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data: N/A

Source of Pre-Existing data: N/A

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: N/A

Type of data collected:

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

The WP will contribute to effective visibility and communication of the outcomes of OTTERS as well as related EU initiatives in order to increase awareness of available tools and resources for effective use of citizen science to raise awareness about the challenges faced by aquatic ecosystems, enhance EU's work on ocean literacy and engage young citizen scientists to take up water stewardship, and decision-making.

Process of data collection:

The main part of data collected in this WP is related to quantitative and qualitative data about the communication and dissemination activities. Statistical data about communication and dissemination activities will be generated by the main communication channels, i.e. website, social media accounts.

The data collection will be implemented through the following steps:

- Design and development of project identity & website (Completed; otters-eu.aua.am/)

- Development of a comprehensive Outreach, Communication and Dissemination plan - The plan will be developed to cover both internal and external project communication. The plan will define the key messages of the project, clearly identify specific target end-user groups and define the most appropriate one and two-way channels of communication e.g. Social Media, Posters, Brochures, Workshops, Exhibitions, Business events etc.
- Graphics and communications materials toolbox - This is about the implementation of the channels of communication identified in the OTTERS Plan for the dissemination and exploitation. They will consist of a combination of graphics materials and communication strategies that will provide a comprehensive toolbox for the effective outreach and dissemination to end-users and stakeholders. The toolbox may include:
 - a) OTTERS presentation and report templates,
 - b) Leaflets, flyers, posters and/or banners for promotion of the project and specific products or services to target end-user groups,
 - c) The project website,
 - d) E-Newsletters (at least 3),
 - e) Social Media,
 - f) Press releases,
 - g) Workshops, conferences, focus groups and other events, and
 - h) Scientific publications.

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Work Package 6

WP6 will contain information collected by the project coordinator from project partners in order to facilitate managing the project and ensure smooth communication throughout. The majority of this information will be for internal use within OTTERS, with the exception of information published within the Project Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, WP6 deliverables, including this document, as well as Ethics assessment.

The results are summarised below.

Pre-Existing Data: Yes

Source of Pre-Existing data: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement; Project Proposal

Conditions for use of pre-existing data: Data is available for internal use within OTTERS; no specific conditions applicable.

Type of data collected:

- Observational data
- Experimental data
- Simulation data
- Derived or compiled data
- Reference or canonical data
- Event related data

Aim of this data:

WP6 aims at providing top level management to ensure that the objectives of the project are efficiently and effectively met on time and with the resources budgeted. It provides effective reporting and communication within the project and towards the European Committee. It ensures quality control of deliverables, re-adjustment of the work and corrective measures if necessary.

Process of data collection:

The main part of data collected in this WP is related to the management of technical issues separately from finance & administration. It will be carried out in the following steps:

- Overall coordination – The Governance structure will be confirmed including committees and persons within these committees as well as the roles, responsibilities and activities of the different committees and other decision rules. Communication flow and methods will be established: the communication flow will be bottom-up and top-down through the typical communication methods.
- Data management – Each WP leader will develop a data management plan for their WP. This will require the WP leaders to liaise with each member of their WP and to document
 - i. The precise nature of the data to be gathered,
 - ii. The ethical issues associated with these data and their storage, and
 - iii. The procedures to be adopted to ensure that the data are recorded in a systematic and safe manner.

- Project risk management – After each major stage of the project, the PE will conduct a risk assessment of the achieved results and determine in advance if a correction action is required for the next stages. This includes:
 - i. Reporting any minor deviations from the project plan,
 - ii. Implementing any recommendations in the contingency plan,
 - iii. Drafting additional or alternative contingency plans, if needed,
 - iv. Communicating the conclusions regarding revised strategies to all project members, and
 - v. In the event of more serious problems, convene the GA for the best route forward.

Format of data collected:

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS /.XLSX
- ✓ .PPT /.PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

4. DATA DOCUMENTATION

All data are documented to help interested users to clearly understand and reuse them. For this reason, descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described complementing each dataset.

LEVEL	INFORMATION ELEMENTS
Dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical report for the user to understand how the data were collected and processed. • Citation information to indicate how secondary users cite the data. • Study design, methodology, instruments and measures used.
File or database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the files that make up the dataset (or tables in the database) relate to each other. • The format of the files.
Variable and item level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the object of analysis was produced. • Label explaining the meaning of variables.

File naming & Identifiers

In the OTTERS project, an identifier is used as a reference number or name for a data object. The identifier is a key part of our documentation and metadata.

Some conditions must be guaranteed

- Context information
- Consistency
- Avoid special characters and spaces

When adopting a file name convention strategy, a simple quick access guide has to be provided: e.g. I_P03_R02_2022-05-01

I = interview (What?)

P [n] = participant ID (Which?)

R [r] = researcher ID (Who?)

Date of interview = YYYY-MM-DD (When?)

5. DATA STORAGE AND BACKUP

OTTERS involves the collaboration between 11 beneficiaries and a moderate amount of data will be generated in various activities. To manage such quantities of data, with the aim to follow the FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability and to stimulate the collaboration among partners, a few data storage tools

have been selected. The selection was made having in mind the purposes and the end-users of the data stored, divided in tools appropriate for internal use and daily project activities, and tools for guaranteeing the long-term storage of OTTERS data.

Private and personal data from stakeholders will be stored locally by partners, and only shared internally within the project with express permission from the stakeholder. This data will be used to create statistics on gender ratio/diversity and on previous experience with citizen science and water related projects. If this data is deemed needed and appropriate to be shared publicly, it will be in anonymised, aggregated from and with express permission of participants, for example to report participation in events or workshops.

List of storage tools NOT appropriate for long-term storing of data generated by OTTERS project but used to carry out daily project activities

Google Drive: is a file storage and synchronisation service developed by Google. Google Drive allows users to store files in the cloud (on Google's servers), synchronise files across devices, and share files. In addition to a web interface, Google Drive offers apps with offline capabilities for Windows and macOS computers, and Android and iOS smartphones and tablets. Google Drive encompasses Google Docs, Google Sheets, and Google Slides, which are a part of the Google Docs Editors office suite that permits collaborative editing of documents, spreadsheets, presentations, drawings, forms, and more. Files created and edited through the Google Docs suite are saved in Google Drive.

Local drives, company cloud storage and external portable storage devices: these are storage facilities that do not fall under surveillance of this data management plan. These are very common and convenient for individual short-term storage of data.

Storage tool(s) appropriate for long-term storing of data and to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data generated by OTTERS:

- **Zenodo:** As a complementary deposit approach, Zenodo, the catch-all repository for EC funded research, will support the dissemination of project achievements. These outputs can take the form of processed data, research protocols, reports, project deliverables to be made public, the different versions of the DMP itself, and other project outputs.

Zenodo enables the definition of communities responsible for the curation of their resources. Thus, we have created an OTTERS community in Zenodo. The corresponding community links are as follows:

Collection URL:<https://zenodo.org/communities/otters/>

The above address links directly to the community collection.

Upload URL: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=otters>

The above address will automatically ensure people who use it will have their record added to your community collection.

Curation URL: <https://zenodo.org/communities/otters/curate/>

The above address links to your private curation URL. You will find all uploads pending your curation.

Harvesting URL:

https://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-otters&metadataPrefix=oai_dc

The above address links to a OAI-PMH feed, which can be used by other digital repositories to harvest this community.

Fig. 1: Screenshot of the OTTERS community on Zenodo.

- The EU Citizen Science platform will host CS toolboxes, guidelines, factsheets, infographics, and campaign material produced throughout the project as a Citizen Science Resource Hub. This will increase the findability, accessibility, and sustainability of the produced information beyond the timeline of the project. The OTTERS project will be reached accessible at the following link: <https://eu-citizen.science/project/419>

6. DATA ACCESS

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners. It will be stored in the OTTERS Google Drive. The public data will be accessible as soon as published in open repositories.

The data containing personal data and the data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, workshops and through other data gathering methods used during the project will be anonymised, and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party unless authorised by the individuals concerned via informed consent. Raw data such as interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium and with external open repositories only upon agreement of the participants (agreement via informed consent) and in anonymised form. The stored data will not contain the names or other personal identifiers of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports). In case of sharing the data in an open repository, the following formats would be shared: transcripts, aggregated files, interview guidelines. Finally, citizen science data reports based on interviews, focus groups and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

In case of recording and publishing audiovisual data (workshops, webinars, seminars, etc.) wherein anonymity will be difficult to ensure, all participants will be asked to provide consent about their participation and views being published.

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the respective organisation responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for at least one year after the end of project. Data related to project finances and relevant for reporting duties to the EC will be kept for as long as needed. If requested and agreed by the participants, data can be shared with other consortium members through the online repository.

In case of data that cannot be made accessible to the public, it will be stored in Zenodo (to preserve it) but only the metadata will be publicly accessible (In CC 0).

Research outputs such as reports will be stored in trusted repositories, such as Zenodo, CORDIS, EOSC or the EU Citizen Science platform. The OTTERS project website (<https://otters-eu.aua.am/>) will also be maintained beyond the project's end.

7. DATA SHARING AND REUSE

OTTERS beneficiaries will be the main users of data produced in the project. In OTTERS, all data may be classified into open, sensitive and closed. Access depends on the classification of the data.

- Open data must be acknowledged by citing the data set. Permission from the researcher is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the researcher after any identifying information has been removed. Then, they can be used and cited. Permission from the researcher could be sought.
- Closed data are not available for sharing.

Data security:

We will ensure that all data collected and generated by the project is compliant with the relevant EU and National Legislation such as privacy and data protection regulations (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR). Under no circumstance will the project include, store or process private information, pictures etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. Under no circumstance we will provide personal data to third parties.

Data recovery will be guaranteed by regular data backups of information stored on the shared project folder.

Data Interoperability:

Data and metadata will follow the PPSR Core on Citizen Science projects standards, and will include references to other data and metadata for interoperability. Data will be made available in commonly used/non-proprietary formats (e.g. .txt, .csv, .docx, .pdf, .jpeg, .png, .mp4) to ensure re-use.

8. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

As an increasingly important form of public participation, citizen science projects and initiatives must comply with existing legal frameworks such as data protection laws, intellectual property laws, and health and safety regulations.

Although the legal framework surrounding marine and freshwater related citizen science activities can vary depending on the country and region, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹ provides the overarching set of rules for the protection of personal data in the EU. It applies to all organisations that process personal data of EU citizens, regardless of where the organisation is located.

In the context of OTTERS, compliance with the GDPR's requirements for data protection requires obtaining informed consent from participants, providing clear information about how data will be used, and ensuring that data is stored securely and does not allow identification of persons or other sensitive data.

OTTERS will provide clear and concise information about the project's goals, methods, and expected outcomes. This information will be communicated in a way that is accessible to all participants, regardless of their level of scientific knowledge.

Ethical Considerations

During the campaigns, the co-design processes with external stakeholders, or hackathons/ideathons, collected data will be organised using informed consent forms and meeting notes. We will ask the name, age, gender, whether there is previous experience with citizen science and water related projects. We will also ask the email with the clear specification that this means that they are Opting-in to the OTTERS news mailing list. This news mailing list will be used to send Newsletters and info relevant to the OTTERS project.

The personal data that will be collected and generated by the OTTERS project will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, where possible, thus it is in line with the FAIR principles. Furthermore the coordinator and consortium partners will ensure that the data collected and generated by the project is compliant with the relevant EU and National Legislation such as privacy and data protection regulations (e.g., General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

The personal data that will be collected will not be made openly available as its only purpose is to be used internally to the project to create statistics on the gender ratio and on previous experience with citizen science and water related projects or send project news. Anonymised notes will be used in case any of this information will have to be used outside the consortium. The informed consent forms will be stored in the Google Drive owned by the coordinator (AUA) and will be kept for a maximum of 5 years after the end of the project and deleted as soon as possible.

OTTERS views full compliance with ethical standards as an essential ingredient of the activities that will generate successful outcomes and meaningful impact. In this regard it will tap on the resources of its Consortium members and will adhere to the “Ten principles of citizen science”² set out by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), a leading partner in OTTERS. These principles are widely recognized as a framework of standards to foster excellence in all aspects of citizen science. More specifically, the key ethical considerations in OTTERS related to the data management/sharing/ownership will include:

1. *Informed consent: Participants will be fully informed about the goals of the project, the risks involved, and their rights as participants. They will also be given the opportunity to withdraw from the project at any time.*

In practice, this means that the OTTERS consortium members will provide participants with a clear and concise explanation of what the study involves, including what data will be collected and how it will be used. Participants will also be informed about any potential risks associated with participating in the study, such as risks to their privacy or safety. Finally, participants will be encouraged to ask questions and have those questions answered before deciding whether or not to participate.

2. *Data privacy: Participants' personal data will be protected from unauthorised access or use.*

Data privacy (the protection of personal data from unauthorised access or use) is an important consideration in citizen science projects.

To ensure that participants' personal data is protected from unauthorised access or use, OTTERS will aim to use wherever possible data collection methods that minimise the amount of personal data collected, or use data collection methods that have been shown to be effective at protecting participants' personal data.

² <https://www.ecsa.ngo/ecsa-guidelines-and-policies/>

3. *Data quality: Data collected by participants will be of high quality and accuracy.*

Data quality is an important consideration in OTTERS. In order for data collected by participants to be useful, it must be of high quality and accuracy. One of the main concerns with citizen science is the potential for compromised data quality. Since citizen scientists may lack formal training and expertise, there is a risk of inaccurate or unreliable data being collected. This can pose challenges for researchers who rely on high-quality data for their studies.

Bias and Sampling Issues: Citizen science projects often rely on volunteers who may not represent a diverse cross-section of the population. This can introduce bias into the data, leading to skewed results that may not be representative of the broader population. Additionally, citizen science projects often have limited geographic coverage, which can further limit the generalizability of the findings.

This means that researchers will take steps to ensure that data collected by participants is reliable and free from errors.

To ensure data quality, the OTTERS consortium will provide participants with clear instructions on how to collect data and, if required, training on how to use any equipment or tools required for data collection.

OTTERS partners will also establish quality control measures to ensure that data collected by participants is reliable and free from errors. This may include using multiple participants to collect data or using statistical methods to identify and correct errors in the data.

4. *Data ownership: Participants will have a say in how their data is used and shared.*

To ensure that participants have a say in how their data is used and shared, OTTERS will provide participants with clear information about how their data will be used and who will have access to it. The OTTERS consortium will also obtain informed consent from participants before collecting any personal data. This means that participants will be informed about the purpose of the research, what data will be collected, how it will be used, and who will have access to it.

References

European Commission Data Protection webpage

Link: https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) “Ten principles of citizen science”

Link: <https://www.ecsa.ngo/ecsa-guidelines-and-policies/>

OTTERS Grant Agreement_101094094

Link: Grant Agreement-101094041-OTTERS.pdf

OTTERS Consortium Agreement

Link: OTTERS CA.pdf

OTTERS Project Proposal

Link: PROPOSAL_101094041-OTTERS-HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-05.pdf

